

Workshop Output Report: Phosphorus Sustainability Roadmapping

December 2022

Phosphorus Forum, Sustainable Phosphorus Summit

Raleigh, North Carolina

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7387236](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7387236)

RTI Innovation Advisors

Introduction

The field of phosphorus sustainability is rapidly developing to meet complex challenges with the capacity to alter not only physical, life, social, and economic sciences, but society as a whole. The wicked problem of phosphorus (P) plaguing sustainability is that all living things need phosphorus as it is an essential nutrient for animals, plants and microbes, and society's unsustainable usage of phosphorus is endangering both the environment and its inhabitants, at present.

In efforts to support the continuous need for phosphorus while simultaneously contributing to the challenges of the field, the National Science Foundation (NSF) Science and Technology Center (STC) has funded the Science and Technologies for Phosphorus Sustainability (STEPS) Center. The STEPS Center is a convergence research community of diverse and leading scientists working tirelessly to achieve actionable goals that can reduce human dependence on phosphorus, enhance resilience of food systems, and reduce environmental damage.

The STEPS vision is to facilitate a 25% reduction in human dependence on mined phosphates and a 25% reduction in losses of point and non-point sources of phosphorus to soils and water resources within 25 years. Though actionable, the research and dedication needed to achieve this goal requires the best of all of our energies and skills.

To reach the 25-in-25 vision, STEPS is catalyzing collective action. This will be done through the creation of an industry roadmap that will articulate how this might be done and who will be necessary, grounded in scientific advances but inclusive of the full ecosystem and will concentrate on a national (USA) viewpoint. The act of creating a roadmap requires a diverse set of stakeholders to convene and align on a goal or vision that will inspire the broader community to act towards. STEPS has made its mission to turn this industry roadmap into impact that reaches well beyond the organizations involved in writing it.

This document summarizes the stakeholder input received during the November 2022 Phosphorus Forum at the Sustainable Phosphorus Summit in Raleigh, NC. Over 120 stakeholders from industry, government, academia, NGOs with a range of expertise participated. The goal of this workshop was to receive feedback and input from a diverse set of stakeholders on a phosphorus sustainability roadmap centered on the 25-in-25 vision.

Key Takeaways

1

Stakeholder optimism is apparent

Across all present stakeholders, there is commitment and clear optimism regarding tackling P sustainability. For these leaders, the question is not “if”, but rather “how”?

2

Communication is key

Efficient and accurate communication is needed both between stakeholders and the public. To achieve P sustainability goals, it's imperative that stakeholders and the broader public have a comprehensive understanding and knowledge of phosphorus sustainability, which will require increasing education, engagement, and interest surrounding P. This includes providing academics with a granular understanding of what all the players in industry encompass, communicating with stakeholders to understand demand and needs within industry, and most importantly, emphasizing citizen science and public engagement.

3

Technology is seen as an enabler, but not a final solution

Modern technology allows us to Incentivize behavior and inform policy changes by enabling quantification of important metrics, including water quality and environmental impacts. However, stakeholders agreed that alone, technology is insufficient to solve these problems, so it's crucial that additional action is taken.

4

Solutions must be scale and context specific

Teams articulated that solutions cannot be one size fits all. They need to be reflective of the scale and different regulatory environments, as well as the environment and ecology of an area.

Key Takeaways

5

Legacy P must be prioritized in the roadmap

During the workshop, participants ideated around the complexities of soil P in groups. From this, the importance of legacy P was made evident.

6

Key Stakeholders were missing

The Phosphorus Forum brought in a diverse set of stakeholders. However, there were still important groups missing including farmers or representatives from farming organizations, food processors, different sectors involved in food consumption, and representatives from the finance and insurance industries. There was also agreement upon the value of voices from impacted communities, including regulators, biotech firms, agricultural stakeholders with farmer networks, food retailers, grocery stores, food processors, restaurants and more. Identifying and hearing from these parties is an ongoing commitment and has been a focus of complementary work within STEPS that will be incorporated into the roadmap.

7

The roadmap development process continues

Moving forward, it's crucial to flesh out the Impact Opportunities with more specific actions, clear objectives and performance metrics. Participants detailed potential stakeholders that are critical to include as well as any concerns or missing components that will be reviewed. In addition, we will consider the potential for unintended consequences to ensure the strategic roadmap reflects the complexities of this wicked problem.

Impact Opportunities

A successful roadmap is predicated on alignment across a diverse set of stakeholders on actions required to reach an agreed upon vision. The overarching goal of the workshop was to achieve this through receiving feedback from a diverse set of stakeholders on drafted Impact Opportunities.

An Impact Opportunity is a set of large scale, collective actions that drive progress towards the realization of the 25-in-25 vision. These must be:

- Essential to the vision
- Deviate from business as usual
- Require collective action
- Stand the test of time

In assessing these drafted Impact Opportunities, participants were asked to grapple with and vote on:

Which Impact Opportunities will generate the most commitment among key stakeholders?

Additionally, stakeholders discussed:

- How might you or your field, sector or industry contribute to this Impact Opportunity
- What must we be aware of or what might be missing in this Impact Opportunity
- What connections across other P-Flow categories might be needed?

Resonant Impact Opportunities

- 1** Improve P efficiency in agricultural systems by processing animal and food waste nutrients economically for on-farm applications, enabled by increased collaboration and stakeholder engagement
- 2** Elevate P in public consciousness and promote awareness of P sustainability to encourage society support for change
- 3** Produce highly valuable products from the P recovery process
- 4** Improve P monitoring to enable implementation of existing environmental regulations with enforceability, accountability and economic pressures
- 5** Accelerate technology development and adoption through active stakeholder engagement
- 6** Close waste loops in the food value chain
- 7** Reduce mining waste (and non-mining) by safely reprocessing and repurposing it for new P products (including P fertilizer)
- 8** Build strong partnerships with the diverse industries affected by poor P management and connect people with reasons to care about natural resources

Top Impact Opportunities

1

Improve P efficiency in agricultural systems through collaborative innovations and stakeholder engagement synergistically with processing animal and food waste nutrients consistently and economically for on-farm applications

“This enables localized solutions to P pollution and can act as an alternative revenue stream for producers”

”Holistic thinking is needed and can beneficially tie into circularity conversations in other markets”

2

Elevate P in public consciousness and promote awareness of P sustainability and wickedness of problem to encourage society support for change

“Stakeholders really felt that the promotion and public education on P sustainability was an important precursor for the changes suggested throughout the day”

3

Produce highly valuable products from the P recovery process

“There are tremendous opportunities here and plenty of potential end users”

“Seems like a space where a lot of different stakeholders and scientist have matching interests which could be leveraged”

Other Discussed Impact Opportunities

Most votes

- Jumpstart P recovery technology development and adoption through policy incentives
- Incentivize equitable transitions to lower P footprint diets through structural and market changes
- More tightly link conservation practices with farming incentives and disincentives
- Accelerate technology development and adoption speed through active stakeholder engagement
- Connect people with reasons to care about natural resources (ecosystem services) such as modeling connecting quantitative/qualitative
- Develop public outreach platforms to better educate about the links between P and water quality
- Create a trusted source of relevant pools of P through verified data and models
- Improve awareness and education through storytelling
- Better use the unused forms of P in soil
- Creation of decision support tools for P management decisions that reflect uncertainty related to farm scale
- Focus on optimizing fertilizer use and improve distribution
- Include P in the holistic management of plant nutrients
- Create a unified group of [farm] extensions to communicate all impact opportunities to growers, industry and policy makers
- Consider changes to animal feeding such as probiotics, phytase, whey, bone-meal and insects
- Identify time-lags for water quality improvements
- Re-evaluate plant selections to those that are more efficient at P acquisition
- Include biological inputs training programs through the extension programs
- Diversify P application and uses to help commit industries to accept reduce P use
- Include P in existing and new sustainability, climate or similar certifications
- Strengthen international collaboration and communication networks to understand successes and failures of policy experiments
- Expand markets for novel alternative agricultural products

Workshop Details: P-Flow Categories

P-Flow Diagram

*Flow diagram inspired by Cordell and White, Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour. 2014. 39:161-88

P-Flow Categories

For simplicity at the workshop, the P-flow diagram was condensed into 5 P-flow categories, which participants self-sorted into.

Workshop Details: *Morning Session*

Building the Future of Phosphorus Together:

Stakeholders were challenged with creating a phosphorus sustainability roadmap based on the 25-in-25 vision, complete with discussions about what stakeholders asked to see from the roadmap we are building, as well the power of roadmapping and preliminary results on what surveyed stakeholders believe to be the urgent and long-term challenges around P sustainability.

How Do We Achieve Phosphorus Sustainability?

Participants were asked to self-sort into one of the five different P-flow categories and then for feedback on multiple drafted Impact Opportunities using the below questions as prompts:

- What might be the strengths and positives about this Impact Opportunity?
- What might be concerns about this Impact Opportunity?
- What might be new or other ideas to consider about this Impact Opportunity?

As a group, participants then discussed the below questions:

- Which Impact Opportunities resonated with you and why?
- Which Impact Opportunities did not resonate with you and why?
- What Impact Opportunities might be missing?

Workshop Details: *Afternoon Session*

What and Who Do We Need to Achieve Phosphorus Sustainability?

For the top two voted Impact Opportunities, participants were asked to ideate further. Using the below questions, participants were asked to brainstorm:

- Who might we need to achieve this impact opportunity?
- What actions might we take to achieve this impact opportunity?
- What resources might you and/or your industry offer that would help achieve this impact opportunity?

As a group, participants then discussed the below questions:

- Which stakeholders rose to the top to achieve the Impact Opportunity and why?
- Which actions rose to the top to achieve the Impact Opportunity and why?
- Which stakeholders and actions might be missing to achieve the Impact Opportunity?

Explore What We've Created

Showcasing the work done thus far in the day, all top-voted Impact Opportunities across the 5 P-flow categories were organized into a gallery walk. During the gallery walk, participants voted for the four Impact Opportunities that they believe will generate the most commitment among key stakeholder and were able to provide feedback on Impact Opportunities outside of their focus.

How We Move Forward Together

To close, the top Impact Opportunity in each P-Flow category was highlighted in a large group discussion and stakeholders were given a chance to voice any opinions or thoughts. Participants were also given an opportunity to sign up to participate further in the roadmap development process.

Acknowledgements

Thank you to all the attendees for their thoughtful responses and lively discussion throughout the workshop.

STEPS is funded by the National Science Foundation (NSF) under Grant No. CBET-2019435.

Special thanks to those who helped with the below components of the workshop:

P Week Organizers

- Olga Borquez, Arizona State University
- Jasmine Covington, North Carolina State University
- Maude Cuchiara, North Carolina State University
- Jim Elser, Arizona State University
- Brenda Gainey, North Carolina State University
- Khara Grieger, North Carolina State University
- Keyon Kemp, North Carolina State University
- Matt Scholz, Arizona State University

Workshop organizers

- Jessie Man, RTI Innovation Advisors
- Taylor Moot, RTI Innovation Advisors
- Cary Strickland, RTI Innovation Advisors

Facilitators

- Justin Baker, North Carolina State University
- Doug Call, North Carolina State University
- Jessica Deaver, North Carolina State University
- Alison Deviney, North Carolina State University
- Jim Elser, Arizona State University
- Brailey Faris, RTI Innovation Advisors
- Khara Grieger, North Carolina State University
- Sandra Guzman, University of Florida
- Christine Hendren, Appalachian State University
- Brooke Mayer, Marquette University
- Ashton Merck, North Carolina State University
- Amanda Rose, RTI Innovation Advisors
- Ross Sozzani, North Carolina State University

Draft Impact Opportunity Development

- Justin Baker, North Carolina State University
- Treavor Boyer, Arizona State University
- Doug Call, North Carolina State University
- John Classen, North Carolina State University
- Jessica Deaver, North Carolina State University
- Alison Deviney, North Carolina State University
- Owen Duckworth, North Carolina State University
- Jim Elser, Arizona State University
- Luke Gatiboni, North Carolina State University
- Khara Grieger, North Carolina State University
- Shin-Ah Lee, University of Florida
- Brooke Mayer, Marquette University
- Ashton Merck, North Carolina State University
- Rebecca Meunich, Arizona State University
- Kelly Morgan, University of Florida
- Bruce Rittman, Arizona State University
- Matt Scholz, Arizona State University

STEPS Management Team

- Justin Baker, North Carolina State University
- Jasmine Covington, North Carolina State University
- Maude Cuchiara, North Carolina State University
- Christine Hendren, Appalachian State University
- Jacob Jones, North Carolina State University
- Paul Westerhoff, Arizona State University
- Ross Sozzani, North Carolina State University

RTI Innovation Advisors Support

- Kyra Pfeiffer, RTI Innovation Advisors

